

On the presence of *Holcocranum saturejæ* (Kolenati, 1845) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Artheneidae) on the Greek island of Crete

Torsten van der Heyden

Immenweide 83, D-22523 Hamburg, Germany.

E-mail: tmvdh@web.de ORCID iD: 0000-0003-4138-7160

ABSTRACT: The first confirmed record of *Holcocranum saturejæ* (Kolenati, 1845) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Artheneidae) on the Greek island of Crete is reported. The distribution of the species is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Holcocranum saturejæ*, first record, distribution, Crete, Greece.

Holcocranum saturejæ (Kolenati, 1845) has been reported (Dorow & Schneider, 2021; Aukema, 2025), but no specific record of the species from the Greek island of Crete has been reported, so far. Herein, the first record of *H. saturejæ* from Crete is reported: On 08.02.2024, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was observed and photographed on the Akrotiri peninsula, located in the north-western part of the island (coordinates: 35.56981557, 24.1310368401, accuracy: 679 m).

The species was introduced to the United States of America (Hoffman & Slater, 1995) and to Argentina (Carpintero et al., 2021).

The presence of *H. saturejæ* in Greece

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Holcocranum saturejæ* (Kolenati, 1845), Akrotiri peninsula, Crete, Greece, 08.02.2024. (Photo: Fotis Samaritakis).

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